

The Coupling Constants Series and Curvature Vortexes – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the first representation of the coupling constants series, i.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor; it is possible to construct a new way to represent the trait of spin, as a curvature vortex. Such a representation is valid as spin is regarded as the second representation of the coupling series. The prime critical line attained the spin representation.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.21)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

Shifting to spin representations for the second to fifth bosonic interactions:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

We have proven bosons to be closed ripples on the matrix tensor, as they are part of a cyclic group, generated by the same element. I.e. the invariant (3).

$$(e) = (3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.14)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.15)$$

Now, since we have the spin representation, that ripple or net curvature on the matrix tensor should have a vortex to it, a spin over a fixed axis that causes the electrons to align on opposite directions, as presented on the Feynman diagrams.

The green inner arrow represent the vortex direction, which is the spin trait by the second representation. The curvature ripple is not a static entity but rather a vortex on the matrix tensor. It is a valid claim is we can represent each bosonic emission by the spin representation, yielding exactly spin one. Therefore, the overall result of such a construction is an additional way to visualize and understand spin. In the 8T spin can be represented as a net curvature vortex on the matrix tensor, the vortex is curvature unbound as it not within the bracket, and emitted and absorbed by matter. Since it is unbound, it can propagate independently of matter, similar to bosonic fields in physical theories.

References

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